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DIMENSIONS" OF THE LEXICO-SEMANTIC SYSTEM

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Abstract: *This article examines lexical-semantic systems, reveals the systematic nature of vocabulary and its various dimensions.*

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What is the lexical-semantic system of language?

A kind of "cell" of the lexical-semantic system, revealing the systematic nature of vocabulary (its various "dimensions") and reflecting the corresponding "piece", segment of reality, is an elementary unit, which can be tentatively called a "word-concept" [1; p.291], i.e. a word in one of its meanings. In the dictionary of S.I. Ozhegov's noun sister two such units are merged: sister₁ - "the daughter of the same parents or one of them in relation to their other children" and sister₂ - "a member of the mid-level medical staff in medical institutions". The lexical unit sisters is included in the semantic field of kinship terms as having in its meaning the corresponding feature indicating belonging to this field: $x(\text{sister}_1) \in M(\text{brother, father, mother, son, daughter, grandfather, grandmother, grandson, granddaughter, uncle, aunt, etc.})$. Another unit sister₂ is included accordingly in the semantic field of designations of medical personnel: $y(\text{sister}_2) \in M_1(\text{nurse, orderly, nanny, paramedic, physician, doctor, etc.})$. The fundamental possibility of a consistent description of vocabulary by distributing its units ("words-concepts") across semantic fields is one of the evidences of its systemic organization. Practical confirmation of this is the experience of work in the field of compiling ideographic dictionaries [1; p. 291], or thesauri. A thesaurus is a dictionary in which words are arranged not in alphabetical order, but according to certain conceptual spheres. In the well-known Roger dictionary (P.M. Roger. Thesaurus of English Words and Phrases), which has gone through many editions, there are six main conceptual spheres, or classes: "abstract relations", "simple equality", "matter", "reason", "will", "feelings". These classes are divided into 24 subclasses and then into 1000 topics. Each of the 1000 topics contains units of similar meaning, closely related by a common conceptual content. Such dictionaries are lists of semantically homogeneous "words-concepts" in each rubric with their possible synonyms and antonyms. Words arranged in paradigms in this way can be described quite strictly within a given microsystem using a certain set of indices.

The units sestrah₁ and sestrah₂, being in certain oppositions with the corresponding "words-concepts", are included not only in the paradigm fields, but also enter, realizing their meaning in the language, into regular connections with quite specific lexical units, i.e. form syntagma fields: sestrah - native, cousin, half-sister, younger, older sister, brother and sister, someone's sister or someone's sister, etc.; sister₂ – a medical sister (nurse), a nurse on duty, a nurse, a housekeeper, etc. Research in the field of word compatibility (in particular, lexical syntagmatics) helps to reveal the pattern of linear arrangement of text units, determined by their semantic agreement. A striking

manifestation of the systematic nature of vocabulary is the ability to economically interpret non-free word compatibility using a limited set of lexical functions [2; pp. 42-50].

The units under consideration, like other similar ones, enter into certain connections with each other (based on the identity of their linguistic shells and the motivation of meanings), forming the structure of a polysemantic word: $sister_1 \leftrightarrow sister_2$ “daughter of the same parents or one of them in relation to their other children $\leftrightarrow$ a member of the mid-level medical staff in medical institutions”. The connection, the rapprochement of meanings is based here on the associative features of gender (female) and closeness: cf., on the one hand, our, your, their sister (i.e. we, you and those like us (them) – about women) and, on the other – She is like a sister to us, takes care of the sick, like a (real) sister; the word sister generally indicates something close, related: Oh, muse! our song is sung. // Come, close the poet's eyes // To the eternal sleep of non-existence, // Sister of the people – and mine! (N.A. Nekrasov. To the Muse). The secondary meaning of the word sister (in the Dictionary of Church Slavonic and Russian Language of 1847 and in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Living Great Russian Language by V.I. Dahl it is not yet presented and comes into use later) appears in associative links as a specification of the primary: "relative, close person $\leftrightarrow$ caring, close woman, girl $\leftrightarrow$ woman, girl, caring for the sick, taking care of them."

Polysemy is one of the most important "dimensions" of the lexical-semantic system, one of the manifestations of the regular connection of elementary lexical units that form a certain hierarchy of interdependent primary and secondary semantic functions in the structure of a polysemantic word. Systemic connections of vocabulary are reflected in such internally related categories as synonymy and antonymy; they cover wide layers vocabulary, and above all words (units) with the meaning of quality of a feature (property), action-state, relationship, etc., playing an exceptionally important role in the language, constituting the core of its abstract vocabulary. As can be seen, the lexical-semantic system of language, being a necessary component of the general system of language, reflects in our consciousness the essential properties of extra-linguistic reality and plays an important role in the organization and regulation of relations between man (more broadly - linguistic society) and the surrounding world, in the cognition of the laws of objective reality.

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